

STANDARD OPERATING PROCEDURES FOR PARENTAGE-BASED TAGGING FOR LAKE ONTARIO CHINOOK SALMON USING MICROSATELLITE DATA

A project report to the NY State Department of Environmental Conservation Great Lakes Unit.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Parentage-based tagging – genetically matching hatchery-raised fish with their broodstock parents – is rapidly gaining popularity as a resource-efficient approach to marking and identifying hatchery-raised fish (Anderson & Garza, 2006). First, tissue samples are collected from all members of the broodstock or at least one parent of all spawned fish during annual spawning runs and broodstock collections (Fig. 1.1 A). These samples are genotyped and used to make up the genetic reference library to which putative offspring samples are compared (Fig. 1.1 B). Hatchery-origin fish inherit their DNA from their broodstock parents and are thus “marked from birth” (Fig. 1.1 C) while their naturally reproduced counterparts are not the offspring of the broodstock and are “unmarked” (Fig. 1.1 D). Post-stocking and outmigration, both hatchery-origin and wild-origin fish mix in the population (Fig. 1.1 E), fish can then be sampled from this population during routine surveys to estimate the proportion of hatchery and wild fish at-large (Fig. 1.1 G). Sampled fish are genotyped and then compared to the broodparents in the genetic reference library using parentage analyses (Fig. 1.1 H). Fish that are statistically determined to be the offspring of a broodstock parent are considered “hatchery-origin” while fish that do not match with a parent are assumed to be “wild-origin” or naturally reproduced fish. To continue the marking program, tissue samples can be collected from all broodparents that return to the hatchery (Fig. 1.1 F). Parentage-based tagging programs have been successfully implemented for hatchery-augmented salmon populations along the Pacific Coast of the US with accuracy rates exceeding 99% (Hargrove et al., 2021; Steele et al., 2013) and several smaller pilot studies have been conducted in herring (Evans et al., 2018), Pallid Sturgeon (*Scaphirhynchus albus*; DeHaan et al., 2008), and Burbot (*Lota lota*; Campbell et al., 2019).

Figure 1.1: (Reproduced from Fitzpatrick et al. 2023) Implementing parentage-based tagging as a mass marking program to distinguish between hatchery-origin (purple) and wild-origin fish (green), can be incorporated into existing management procedures. Stages are described in text.

Chinook Salmon are the most popular recreational fishery in Lake Ontario and the population is supported by natural reproduction and annual hatchery augmentation by the New York State Department of Environmental Conservation (NYSDEC) and the Ontario Ministry of Natural Resources and Forestry (MNRF). While stocking levels are updated regularly in response to changing prey fish availability, monitoring of whole-lake natural reproduction has been sporadic (though see Bishop et al., 2020 for Salmon River, NY monitoring). While mass marking programs have been previously implemented (Connerton et al., 2016), an annual long-term natural reproduction monitoring program does not currently exist for the entire Lake Ontario population. Parentage-based tagging holds promise as being an accurate and resource-efficient tool for supporting a long-term mass marking program for distinguishing hatchery and wild-origin Chinook Salmon in Lake Ontario.

The Lake Ontario Chinook Salmon population poses challenges to parentage-based tagging given the genetic history of the stock. The entire population is descendent from a single source strain (“Donaldson”; Parsons, 1973) and has remained genetically isolated since the 1980s. Further, there is the potential for non-parent-offspring familial relationships between hatchery broodstock and wild-origin fish as Salmon River, NY is both the source of the NYSDEC hatchery broodstock and considered to be the largest single source of natural Chinook Salmon reproduction for Lake Ontario. Thus, hatchery-origin fish spawn in the Salmon River while wild-origin fish are included in the broodstock (Connerton et al., 2016). The objectives of the pilot study were to estimate the accuracy of parentage-based tagging under these population genetic conditions while determining the resource demand of implementing a long-term monitoring plan.

The pilot study for the implementation of parentage-based tagging for Lake Ontario Chinook Salmon began with collecting tissue samples from all broodmothers used in October 2018 by NYSDEC and MNRF and known-origin hatchery and wild fish in Spring 2019. The results of the study are published in Fitzpatrick et al. (2023). Only broodmothers were collected and used for the study, which reduced the cost and labor needed for genetic analyses but added an additional challenge for accurately identifying natal origin. The study found that parentage-based tagging accurately identified 94% of known hatchery-origin fish by matching them back to a 2018 broodmother and 98% of known wild-origin fish collected from the Salmon River, NY by not matching them with any broodmother.

Included herein are the sampling and analysis protocols that were developed during the Lake Ontario Chinook Salmon parentage-based tagging pilot study. The protocols are divided into three stages: 1) the collection of tissue samples from fish relevant to implementing and assessing a parentage-based tagging program 2) the laboratory protocols for extracting and amplifying DNA from tissue samples and preparing the samples for sequencing and 3) filtering the sequencing products, generating genotypes, and performing the parentage analyses. These protocols provide knowledge to facilitate hand-off and continuation of the Lake Ontario Chinook Salmon parentage based tagging monitoring program. We anticipate that these protocols may continue to develop if a long-term parentage-based tagging program is implemented for Lake Ontario Chinook Salmon.

2. PROTOCOLS FOR THE COLLECTION OF TISSUE SAMPLES

Parentage-based tagging relies on the collection and preservation of tissue samples to obtain the accurate genotypes of the broodmothers and their putative offspring. Tissue samples are collected from three different groups of fish: (1) broodmothers for the creation of the broodstock reference library, (2) fish collected from the population at-large for estimating the proportion stocked, and (3) known origin samples to validate the accuracy of the parentage-based tagging analyses. Tissue collection and storage is relatively straightforward, fin clips are collected, stored in 95% ethanol, and then frozen until DNA extractions can begin. A combination of 95% ethanol and -20°C freezer storage as quickly as possible is generally considered the best way to reduce DNA degradation, though a sample stored in ethanol at room temperature will likely remain viable for several months if not years. Storage in 70% ethanol may be insufficient for preventing sample degradation. Data on the collected samples used in the pilot analysis and in the follow-up 2020-2022 analyses can be found in Appendix 3.

2.1 Types of samples used for parentage-based tagging

Broodmother collections:

Broodmother collections are used to create the broodmother reference library to which putative hatchery-origin fish are compared. If a broodmother is missing from the reference library due to a missing tissue sample or if the sample fails to provide an accurate genotype, it will be impossible to identify that broodmother's offspring as hatchery-origin. *Thus, collecting a tissue sample from each broodmother is critical for accurate identification of hatchery-origin fish.* Data on the year of collection and the location of the collection is useful for determining the age and hatchery-of-origin for any offspring collected in future analyses.

Figure 2.1: Chinook Salmon tissue sample collections for the pilot parentage-based tagging program. In Fall 2018, adipose fin clips were collected from broodmothers at NYSDEC Salmon River Hatchery (A; purple site in B) and along the Credit and Ganaraska Rivers by MNR staff (green and blue sites; B). In Spring 2019 hatchery-origin offspring of the collected broodmothers were collected from NYSDEC and MNR hatcheries while naturally reproduced parr were collected from Salmon River (red site in B; C). B reproduced from Fitzpatrick et al. (2023)

Known-origin sample collections: Known-origin fish were used to estimate the accuracy of parentage-based tagging at identifying hatchery-origin and wild-origin fish. Four sets of known-origin samples were included in the pilot analyses. Three were the offspring of the three sets of broodmothers collected in 2018 by NYSDEC (Salmon River Hatchery; Prindle & Bishop, 2020) and MNR (Credit River and Ganaraska River; Yuille, 2019). The fourth set were known wild-origin fish collected from Salmon River (Bishop et al., 2020). While Chinook Salmon are known to spawn in many Lake Ontario tributaries, the Salmon River is considered the single largest source of natural reproduction, and both hatchery-origin and wild-origin fish spawn in the river. Thus, the resulting fish have the greatest have the highest probability of familial (excluding parent-offspring) relationships with the Salmon River Hatchery broodmothers. Including known-origin samples in future analyses can be used to evaluate any changes in protocols or analyses and ensure that the methods accurately identify hatchery and wild-origin fish.

Fish from population: Collections from fish in the population at-large can be used to estimate the proportion of the population that is of hatchery-origin. However, as with any mass marking method, accurate estimates rely on the sampled fish being a true “random” sample collected without bias. Potential sources of bias include but are not limited to: staging behavior prior to spawning (spatial bias), fishing gear selectivity to wild and hatchery-origin fish (potential size bias), and changes in the proportion stocked for a cohort at-large due to differential mortality between wild and hatchery-origin fish. Prior marking studies for Lake Ontario Chinook Salmon (Connerton 2015) may provide insights into these biases. *Additionally, to use these samples to estimate the proportion stocked the age of the sampled fish must be known.* Without age data, it is impossible to determine the cohort of any wild-origin fish.

2.2 Adult adipose fin tissue collection protocols

Adipose fin tissue were collected from broodmother at the hatchery and from harvested fish collected during the annual NYSDEC creel survey. While only a portion of larger fin clips (≥ 1 cm) are used during the genetic analyses, this size allows enough tissue to be used for multiple rounds of DNA extraction (i.e. if a sample fails to amplify). Smaller tissue sample sizes may be insufficient for additional rounds of DNA extraction. Larger tissue samples are particularly important for ensuring that all broodmothers are represented in the reference library. See Appendix 1 for example datasheets and field protocols.

1. Clip ~ 1cm of the adipose fin using nail nippers or scissors. The clip should be slightly larger than a pencil eraser. In the rare case that the adipose fin is missing, take a clip from the top of the caudal fin. For catch-and-release fish, the tissue samples can be collected non-lethally.
2. Place the clip into a microcentrifuge tube filled with 95% ethanol. Use the forceps or a gloved finger to maneuver the clip into tube if needed.
3. Make sure the tube has an identifying label and record any necessary information (i.e. date of collection, location of collection, type of collection, corresponding agency identification numbers).

4. Ideally within 72 hours carefully replace the ethanol in the microcentrifuge tube with fresh 95% ethanol for best long-term storage. Tissue samples release water during storage, diluting the ethanol that they are stored in and can lead to sample degradation.
5. For long-term storage, store microcentrifuge tube in a -20°C freezer and periodically change ethanol (6 months – 2 years) due to ethanol evaporation to maintain sample quality.

Bulk tissue collection (adults): Caudal fin clips from the broodmothers collected by MNRF have always been collectively stored in ethanol prior to being transferred to Cornell University where they were separated into individual vials and given individual identifying labels. We found no discernable difference in DNA amplification between the individually stored and bulk stored samples, however individual storage has additional benefits over bulk storage. First, individually stored samples allow for biological data (e.g. age, length, weight, condition) from the sampled fish to be linked to the genetic data. This can provide the opportunity for future analyses to examine how biological characteristics, fish origin, and genotypes are related. Second, individual storage can reduce the potential of missing a fin clip during genetic analyses or duplicating a sample. When stored in ethanol, samples become brittle making it difficult to successfully separate clips stuck together and easy to break fin clips into pieces. Third, individually stored samples make it possible to rerun a small set of samples (i.e. those that fail to amplify) without rerunning the entire set of broodmother samples.

2.3 Fingerling whole fish collection protocols

For our analyses, whole fish were collected and then frozen without ethanol. We found notably poorer DNA amplification rates from these specimens than from the tissues samples stored in ethanol; thus storing the whole fish in ethanol may lead to better results in the future. However, verifying the increased efficiency of these protocols requires further testing. Here we suggest storing the whole fish in 95% ethanol and freezing.

1. Place whole fingerling in jar of 95% ethanol (either individually or in bulk based on collection location).
2. Label jar and place backup ethanol-proof label inside the jar. Record any necessary information (i.e. date of collection, collection location, type of collection, corresponding agency).
3. Change ethanol within 24-72 hours.
4. Place jar in -20°C freezer for long-term storage.

3. PROTOCOLS FOR PREPARATION OF TISSUE SAMPLES FOR DNA SEQUENCING

Though several variations on the protocols were explored during the pilot testing, the ones presented below had the greatest success of producing reliable genotyping results. Fitzpatrick et al. (2023) documents the other primary tested protocol used in the pilot analysis (the “HotShot” method described in Turon et al., (2020)). While successful in other applications, the HotShot method is particularly sensitive to the size of the tissue sample used for DNA extraction, with too large of a piece leading to extraction failure. We found the magnetic bead method here to be more reliable and provided the benefit of stable PCR products that could be frozen and used for future analyses or in case of sequencing failure. Continued refinement of the protocols may be beneficial to explore as new techniques become available or other approaches become more cost-efficient.

Figure 3.1: A small portion of the Chinook Salmon fin clip (3x3mm) is used for the genetic analyses.

Marker development and refinement: An initial set of 100 candidate microsatellites were developed for amplicon sequencing following the protocols described in Marcy-Quay et al. 2020. Briefly, this involved sequencing a genomic library enriched for simple repeats to identify candidate microsatellites. The genomic library used DNA from a single Lake Ontario Chinook Salmon that was collected from the Salmon River Hatchery but not included as member of the broodstock. The candidate microsatellites all consisted of di-, tri-, or tetra-repeats and the amplification products ranged in length from 330 to 350 bp. All pairs of candidate microsatellites were also evaluated for linkage disequilibrium to ensure that all loci were considered independent for the parentage analyses.

A final set of 61 microsatellite loci were retained for the analyses after multiple stages of evaluation. First, pairwise comparisons of all pairs of primers were evaluated for potential conflicts using output generated from the ThermoFisher Multiple Primer tool (16 loci dropped). Second, any loci that failed to sequence (1 loci) or had low read yield post-sequencing were dropped from the analyses (10 loci). Third, as parental analysis relies on allelic diversity, low diversity loci were dropped (3 loci). Finally, any loci that were determined to have high genotyping error based on comparing replicate samples were dropped from the analyses (10 loci).

To change the marker panel, validation testing may be necessary to determine if the new panel has sufficient statistical power to accurately identify parent-offspring relationships among Lake

Ontario Chinook salmon. Additionally, it may take several years to phase-in a new panel to maintain tagging of all hatchery-origin fish in the population at-large. Both broodmother and offspring need to have been sequenced at a sufficient number of the same loci to determine a significant (or insignificant) parent-offspring relationship. This number of loci will vary depending on the genotypes of each fish and the prevalence of those genotypes in the population. Thus, the same marker panel should be used to sequence a broodmother and any of her potential offspring. Since very few Chinook salmon collected during annual surveys are older than 3 years old (oldest confirmed was age-5), than any marker panel could be phased out 4 years after the last set of broodmothers is sequenced using the old panel (Chinook salmon are considered to be age-0 the year they hatch).

Primer concentration: Exploratory testing demonstrated that primer concentrations had substantial impact on the quality and quantity of viable sequences produced for genotyping. The initial concentration used in the analyses of 0.2 μM were deemed too high given the number of primers included in the multiplexes. Reduced concentrations of 0.02 μM were found to have much better sequencing results and are included in the protocols described here. Future testing of the effect of primer concentrations on sequencing results may be beneficial if the marker panel is expanded or if a new marker is developed.

3.1 DNA Extraction from Animal Tissue based on Kucka and Chan (2022)

DNA extraction followed the protocols outlined in Kučka and Chan (2022) with small modifications (included below) for the Therkildsen Lab.

Materials

- PureLink™ Genomic Digestion Buffer (Thermofisher , K182301)
- PureLink™ Genomic Lysis/Binding Buffer (Thermofisher, K182302)
- ProteinaseK, 20mg/mL
- RNaseA (DNase Free), 5 mg/ml
- 200 μL wide orifice pipet tips
- SpeedBeads™ (Cytiva 65152105050250 / Sigma GE65152105050250) or GElifesciences Sera-Mag SpeedBead (65152105050250)
- Adhesive 96-well plate seals (Thermofisher, AB0558)

Tissue lysis

1. Prepare 90 μL PureLink Digestion buffer + 20 μL Protease K (20 mg/mL) for each sample. Pipette 110 μL of the mixture into each strip tube on ice
2. Cut tissue sample into 3x3mm slice and transfer into each sample well.
3. Incubate at 60°C for 1 hour with slow shaking, manually shake every 5 min. Alternatively, incubate overnight without manually shaking.
4. Bring to room temperature. Add 90 μL of PureLink lysis buffer to each well.
5. Incubate at 60°C for 30min with shaking.

6. At room temperature, spin for 5 minutes to pellet solids, 6000x g.
7. [96-well plate preparation] Pipette 75 μ L of magnetic beads into each well of a new 96 well plate.
8. Transfer 150 μ L of lysate to 96 well-plate containing beads, use wide orifice pipet tips (if available), gently mix 5 to 10 times by pipetting.
9. Incubate for 10 min at room temperature. Spin the plate briefly, DNA should now bead on the beads.
10. Place plate on a 96-well magnetic stand for 5 min or till the supernatant is clear and the beads have pelleted.
11. Carefully remove supernatant. Keep the plate on the magnetic stand and do not disturb the beads.
12. Add 150 μ L of fresh 80% ethanol and incubate for 30 sec, then remove the ethanol without disturbing the beads.
13. Repeat step 12 for a second ethanol wash and remove any residual ethanol
14. Remove the plate from magnetic stand.
15. Add 100 μ L of 10mM Tris (pH = 8) to the beads to elute the DNA. Make sure the beads are fully submerged. Seal plate.
16. Incubate at room temperature for 5-10 min then gently invert the plate to resuspend the beads.
17. Incubate at room temperature for 20 min, then spin the plate to collect all liquid at the bottom of the wells.
18. Place the plate on the magnetic stand and wait until the beads have pelleted and the supernatant containing the DNA is clear (5-10 min). Transfer DNA to a new plate for storage.

Magnetic bead preparations

1. Prepare 50 mL of bead buffer by dissolving the following in 35 ml of “molecular biology grade” H₂O: 9 g of PEG8000 (Promega, V3011) (final = 18% PEG8000), 7.3 g NaCl (final = 2.5 M NaCl). Add 500 μ L of 1M Tris-HCl (pH = 8.0) and 100 μ L 0.5M EDTA (pH = 8.0). Can place in a warm water bath (50°C) to help dissolve PEG8000.
2. Add H₂O to 45-50 mL. Keep buffer in a 50 mL Falcon Tube.
3. For 50 ml of bead buffer, use one 1 mL of stock beads. Transfer 1 mL of stock beads into a 1.5 mL Eppendorf tube on magnetic stand. After 1 min, remove and discard supernatant.
4. Use 1 mL of buffer to re-suspend beads and then transfer to the 50 mL bead buffer.
5. Store beads at 4°C and bring to room temperature when ready to use.

3.2 PCR following Qiagen Multiplex PCR handbook protocols for amplification of microsatellite loci using multiplex PCR

Materials

- 2X Qiagen Multiplex PCR *Plus* Master Mix

- Primer stock for each locus
1. Create primer mixes for each multiplex group by combining equal amounts of 0.02 μM of primer stock for each locus (see table X for multiplex assignments)
 2. Per sample, add 1 μL of extraction product to a new 96-well plate with 5 μL of 2X Qiagen Multiplex PCR *Plus* Master Mix, 3 μL of H_2O , and 1 μL of primer mix.
 3. Run PCR with a 5 min activation at 95°C followed by 30 cycles of: 30 sec at 94°C, 90 sec at 56°C, 90 sec at 72°C. Finish with 5 min at 72°C and store at 12°C until ready to use.

3.3 Preparation of individually indexed sequencing library following D'Aloia et al. (2017)

Materials

- Illumina Nextera i5 and i7 dual index adapter primers
 - OneTaq HotStart polymerase
 - 1x OneTaq HotStart buffer
 - 10 μM dNTPs
1. Combine 2 μL of PCR product from each of the two multiplex groups for each individual with 4 μL molecular grade water.
 2. Make a master mix of (per sample) of 0.05 μL of 5 U/ μL OneTaq HotStart polymerase, 2 μL of 5x OneTaq HotStart Buffer, 0.2 μL of 10 μM dNTPs, and 5.25 μL of molecular grade H_2O . Mix vigorously and add to wells.
 3. If doing combinatorial barcoding step 2 can be scaled to make master mixes for each primer used, aiming for a final concentration of 0.5 μM of each primer. If doing dual unique indexing, 1 μL each of 5 μM i5 and i7 primer should be added to each well.
 4. Add 1.5 μL of diluted PCR product (step 1) to each well.
 5. Run PCR with an initial 2 min at 92°C, then six cycles of 94°C for 30 sec, 62°C for 60 sec, and 68°C for 60 sec, finish with 5 min at 68°C and then hold at room temperature.

3.4 Pool samples and AMPure cleanup protocol

Materials

- 80% ethanol
 - AMPure XP beads
1. In a 1.5 ml tube, pool 3 μL of each library.
 2. Add AMPure XP beads (Beckman Coulter) in a 0.7:1 ratio with the total volume of the pooled libraries (for 450 μL of library, use 315 μL of beads). Pipette to mix.
 3. Incubate for 5 min at room temperature.
 4. Put on magnetic stand and weight for solution to clear (5-10 min).
 5. Remove and discard supernatant.

6. Add 1 ml of 80% ethanol to tube. Incubate for 1 min at room temperature then remove and discard ethanol.
7. Repeat step 6 for a second round of cleaning.
8. Remove any residual ethanol
9. Remove tube from magnetic stand.
10. Add 100 μ L of 10mM Tris HCl (pH = 8) and pipette to mix. Incubate for 5 min at room temperature.
11. Put back on magnetic stand until solution clears. Transfer supernatant to new tube and freeze until sequencing.

3.5 Comments on sequencing machines

There are a variety of different machines that can successfully sequence the microsatellite data used in these analyses, indeed two different machines (Illumina HiSeq 2500 and Illumina MiSeq at Cornell University) were used for the pilot analyses and third for the 2022 data (Illumina NovaSeq 6000 via the University of Illinois). We selected these machines because they could efficiently process the number of samples (~1500 fish) and could accommodate the relatively long reads need for the current set of markers (600 paired-end reads). While best practice would be to continue to use the same machine to sequence all samples used in parentage analyses (Lou & Therkildsen, 2022), this is unlikely to be feasible as sequencing technology continues to develop and change. Since samples from broodmothers are collected years before their offspring will show up in routine surveys, it is possible that parents and offspring samples will be sequenced in different batches and on different machines. Running multiple samples with relatively clean genotypes across different sequencing batches may provide a way to account for batch effects and ensure consistency across sequencing runs.

4. PROTOCOLS FOR RUNNING PARENTAGE ANALYSES ON CHINOOK SALMON MICROSATELLITE DATA

4.1 Filtering haplotype data from sequencer

Initial processing of the sequence data was done using a custom bioinformatics pipeline that extracted the data, merged forward and reverse reads, assigned the reads to specific locus-sample pairs, and filtered out low quality reads. The pipeline was developed by Cornell BioTech and the associated code can be found here: https://github.com/avinashkarn/analyze_amplicon/blob/master/analyze_amplicon.pl. Information on the primers for each loci can be found in Appendix 2 and the output from this pipeline is in Appendix 4.

The sample genotypes assigned by this pipeline were not used in our analyses, instead we conducted additional filtering steps in R prior to assigning genotypes.

4.2 Haplotype filtering in R

Additional filtering of the haplotypes was conducted in R (R Core Team, 2022) prior to genotyping to remove any haplotypes that were produced by sequencing error instead of representing true alleles. The code for additional filtering and preparing the data for Cervus can be found in Appendix 7.

First, any sequences that appeared to be from non-targeted loci were removed the analyses. Chinook Salmon are a functionally diploid species and can be treated as such for parentage-based tagging; however Chinook Salmon are partial tetraploids which results in some regions of the genome being near

Figure 4.1: Diagnostic plots for Locus 180 for identifying sequenced non-target regions, numbers on both plots represent how common the haplotype was in the sequences pooled across samples with 1 being the most common haplotype (A). The presence of multiple haplotypes that do not see an increase in the number of motifs for the targeted region with sequence length indicates the potential presence of sequences from a non-targeted region (B).

duplicates of targeted loci (Allendorf & Thorgaard, 1984). During sequencing, some of these non-targeted regions may be amplified along with the targeted loci and will be classified as the targeted loci. The sequences from the non-targeted regions will need to be separated out before determining individual genotypes. We identified potentially problematic loci by visually inspecting plots of sequence length versus the number of replicated tetra-repeat motifs associated with a targeted locus for a unique sequence. Non-targeted regions tend to have minimal variability in the number of motifs regardless of sequence length while the number of motifs increased with sequence length for targeted loci. After visually inspecting the sequences, short loci-specific sequences of base pairs at the beginning of forward and reverse reads were chosen and used to further filter the reads. Additional evaluation may be needed if these loci continue to be used or if new loci are added to the marker panel.

Second, we dropped any unique sequences that had less than 100 reads across all samples used in the analysis ($n > 1500$ samples). While this approach could potentially drop a true but extremely rare allele from the analysis, it had a substantial impact on the speed of the analyses. Further, a sensitivity test showed that dropping these sequences did not affect the resulting genotypes.

Third, the remaining haplotypes were evaluated for stutter based on Turon et al. (2020). Stutter is the result of sequencing error that generates erroneous sequences, typically by dropping one or more of the tandem repeats that occur within a microsatellite sequence. The erroneous sequences need to be identified and removed from the analyses so they are not mistakenly classified as true alleles. To do so, each sequence was evaluated to see if it only occurred when another sequence was present in a sample and if the second sequence always had a greater number of reads than the first. If so it suggests that the sequence is a sequencing by-product of the other, more dominant sequence and is dropped from the analyses.

4.3 Generating individual genotypes

The haplotypes that survived filtering were used to generate individual genotypes based on the unique sequences that had the greatest number of reads per sample. Because cross-contamination and genotyping errors were evident based on our negative and replicate samples respectively (section 6), we elected to use relatively stringent cutoff values. As the lab processes and sample filtering improves, less stringent thresholds may be appropriate and could improve the proportion of genotyped loci per sample. First, we removed any haplotypes with less than 8 reads from consideration for a sample at a given locus. Then we identified the unique sequences that had the highest and second highest number of reads for that sample-locus combination. The allele with the greater number of reads had to have a minimum of 20 reads for that locus, while the second allele needed a minimum of 8 reads. Homozygosity was determined based on a read depth ratio of 0.3, which was calculated by comparing the number of reads associated with the second most common haplotype to the most common haplotype (Baetscher et al., 2018). Only genotypes with less than 30 reads across included haplotypes were retained for the parentage analyses. The typed genotypes for all samples are located in Appendix 5.

4.4 Parentage analysis using Cervus

Parentage assignments and the evaluations of putative parent-offspring relationships were conducted using Cervus (Kalinowski et al., 2007). We selected Cervus for these analyses because it met the criteria necessary for evaluating our data set, specifically 1) handling missing locus data, 2) could evaluate parent-offspring pairs without data on the missing parent and 3) that the analyses were likelihood-based instead of exclusionary and thus could include genotyping error. Further the software has an extensive history of being used for parentage analyses and has been rigorously evaluated. There are comparable alternatives to Cervus that may warrant further consideration, particularly as the number of available software packages increases with the use of parentage-based tagging and other kinship evaluations. For our analyses we also explored using the CKMRsim package (Anderson 2021) in R and Colony (O. R. Jones & Wang, 2010); however CKMRsim has yet to be peer reviewed and Colony uses a full relationship reconstruction to determine parent-offspring relationships. To create a full relationship reconstruction, Colony jointly evaluates all parent-offspring and sibling relationships, thus any two fish with a shared broodmother must be either full or half-siblings. Given given the potential additional familial relationships (e.g. cousins, avuncular relations) between our samples along with the genotyping error in our data, we were hesitant to use half-sibling relationships for determining offspring origin. Jones et al. (2010) provides some additional discussion of useful features and comparisons between common parentage analysis software though slightly outdated.

Briefly, Cervus determines parent-offspring relationships by comparing the genotypes of an offspring and an alleged parent relative to allelic frequencies in the population. Rarer alleles provide greater statistical support for a familial relationship between an offspring and alleged parent than more common alleles as the offspring is less likely to have inherited the rarer allele from a random individual in the population. In contrast, a mismatch in alleles at a locus can either eliminate the alleged parent from further consideration or provide statistical support for the lack of a parent-offspring relationship. The likelihood that the offspring is the genetic descendent of the alleged parent across all loci is then compared to the likelihood the offspring is the product of a random individual in the population using likelihood ratios.

To accomplish these comparisons, the first step in running parentage analysis in Cervus is estimating the allele frequencies for each locus in the population at large. Then a simulation analysis is conducted to estimate statistical thresholds for determining parent-offspring relationships. Finally, all offspring are compared to each alleged parent and a likelihood ratio is calculated for each putative pair. If the calculated ratio exceeds the threshold determined by the simulation, the parent-offspring relationship is deemed statistically supported. For more information on the fundamentals of parentage analyses see Marshall et al., 1998 and Kalinowski et al., 2007 for specifics on incorporation of genotyping error and the specific likelihoods used in Cervus. All output files from the Cervus analyses can be found in Appendix 6.

Parentage-based tagging expands the utility of parentage analyses by using the identified parent-offspring relationships, or lack thereof, to determine the relative abundance of hatchery-origin

fish in the population. Specifically, if all broodmothers are genotyped, then all hatchery-origin offspring should be effectively marked by their inherited genetics. Sampled fish that have a statistically supported parent-offspring relationship with a broodmother are determined to be of hatchery origin while fish that do not match with a single broodmother are assumed to be wild-origin fish. This does assume that all of the broodmother's offspring were spawned at the hatchery, which may not be true for iteroparous species. In those cases, the year the mother was spawned and the age of the offspring when collected can be used to determine if a fish is hatchery-origin. Fish lacking a genetic match could also be the result of failing to collect genetic samples from every relevant broodmother or error during genetic extractions and sequencing. Thus, continuing to refine lab and sequencing methods and ensuring that tissue samples are collected from every broodmother may lead to higher accuracy rates in identifying hatchery and wild-origin fish.

4.5 Additional analyses and samples of interest

Known parent-offspring pairs: For parentage analyses, known parent-offspring pairs provide the best information to evaluate if parentage-based tagging can correctly identify parent-offspring pairs. Given that the offspring must have inherited their DNA from the known parent, these pairs provide the opportunity for validating genotypes and marker panel. However, this requires caretaking for fertilized eggs and/or larval fish until they can be successfully genotyped. We were unable to include any known parent-offspring pairs in this study, but it may be a useful comparison to considered in the future if known pairs can be easily sampled.

Replicate samples: We included several replicated samples in our analyses which greatly helped with refining the marker and evaluating genotyping quality across different sequencing platforms and DNA extraction methods. The genotypes of each sample were compared across each instance of replication to ensure that the loci included in the marker panel could be reliably genotyped and estimate genotyping error. We also used the known hatchery-origin replicated samples and their identified broodmothers as a proxy for known parent-offspring relationships, as each sample reliably matched with one broodmother.

Negative samples: Samples that sequenced without any DNA intentionally added to these wells during DNA extraction and amplification. These samples were critical in determining that that cross contamination had occurred and for prioritizing which samples would need to be re-sequenced.

Colony analyses: In addition to using Cervus, exploratory analyses were run using Colony (Jones & Wang, 2010) to explore kinship relationships between all broodmother and offspring samples. While we believe that the genotyping error in our data was too high to have robust results from Colony, we found that the half-sibling relationships identified by Colony reflected standard hatchery protocols. At Salmon River Hatchery, all broodmothers were given sequential ID numbers based on the order of collection and fertilization of eggs was typically conduct by combining the eggs of two females with four males. The known Salmon River Hatchery half-

siblings identified by Colony generally identified pairs of sequentially numbered mothers with between one and four contributing males. While these results require further evaluation, they do suggest that not only are hatchery-origin offspring being accurately assigned to the correct hatchery, but also to the correct broodmother.

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APPENDIX 1: EXAMPLE BROODMOTHER TISSUE SAMPLE COLLECTION PROTOCOLS

Genetic Sampling of Chinook Salmon Brood Mothers

Protocols v.2021.10.11

Project Objective: We are using parentage-based genetics to distinguish between stocked and wild Chinook Salmon. In the same way that paternity tests are able to statistically determine if two people are related, we use genetics to ask if fish at large in the lake is the offspring of any brood mothers. Fish that genetically match to a brood mother must be stocked fish, while fish that do not genetically match any of the brood mothers must be wild fish. That is why this analysis is dependent on getting fin clips from each and every brood mother.

Supplies

- Microcentrifuge racks that can hold 80 tubes
- Packs of 80 labeled microcentrifuge tubes filled with ethanol
- Extra caps
- Squirt bottle with extra ethanol
- Nail nippers
- Scissors
- Forceps
- Box to hold microcentrifuge racks
- Gloves
- Gallon ziplocks
- Write-in-the-rain paper
- Data sheets (examples below)

Prep before sampling begins (daily)

1. Place all tubes in microcentrifuge racks (80 per rack) in sequential order. The hatchery can process up to 200 females in a single day.
2. Remove the caps from a subset of tubes (I would suggest 50-80). The egg take happens quickly and removing the caps beforehand can be helpful. Cover all tubes either with a plastic bag or place the rack in one of the microcentrifuge boxes. Water will dilute the ethanol and will result in contamination. More tubes can be uncapped while fish are being sorted, but it is best to have ~ 50 uncapped at a time.
3. The tubes will not be filled all the way to allow for room for a sample, but if any are particularly low add extra ethanol.

For each Chinook female:

1. Clip ~ 1cm of the adipose fin using nail nippers or scissors. The clip should be slightly larger than a pencil eraser. In the rare case that the adipose fin is missing, take a clip from the top of the caudal fin.
2. Place the clip into a microcentrifuge tube. Use the forceps or a gloved finger to maneuver the clip into tube if needed.

3. While the tubes will be pre-filled, if the sample is not covered by the ethanol, add more ethanol. If the sample is stuck at the top of the tube, use forceps to push the sample down till it is completely covered or tap the capped tube against a table till the sample falls down.
4. Screw the cap back on to the tube so the clip is not lost and so two clips are not placed in the same tubes.
5. If something goes wrong, record it and the sample number on the data sheet.

For each subset of Chinook females (eggs collected between sorting fish ~15-60 fish)

1. Record the first and last ID number for each subset of fish on daily sample log
2. Females are usually “paired” – two sets of eggs in a single tray for fertilization – record the ID number of any “single” females.

At the end of the day:

1. Fill out data sheets.
2. Make sure caps are tightly screwed onto all tubes. Loose caps with result in ethanol leakage which can lead to cross-contamination and labels peeling off.
3. Place all samples collected from that day into the same gallon ziplock bag.
4. Fill out a label with the collection date, location, and first and last sample ID number and place it in the bag. Do not mix together samples from different days.
5. Recap any open microcentrifuge tubes.
6. If possible, store the samples in a freezer. A normal residential freezer (0°F/-20°C) will work just fine.
7. Make sure that there are sufficient supplies for the next day of sampling and let Kimberly know if you need more.

Storing Samples

1. Make sure all samples bagged together (i.e. from the same day) stay together. Check that bags have all relevant information. Only work on samples from one bag at a time.
2. Check each tube to make sure labels are legible with ID number
3. Change out ethanol in each microcentrifuge tube with fresh 95% ethanol
4. Store samples in the freezer

Notes

- If in doubt, take a genetic sample and make a note about any issues. It is easy to remove a sample from the analysis later, but impossible to recover a missed sample.
- Do not hesitate to reach out with any questions or if more materials are needed.
- Going in sequential order helps with future labeling and reduces confusion if eggs are discarded. If you need to skip a number due to a lost tubes or a mix-up, note it on the data sheet.
- It is important to keep samples separated by day in the event that the eggs from that day are discarded we do not process unnecessary samples.
- Do not take samples from females that are “hard”, unripe, or that eggs are NOT collected from for any reason. If eggs are not taken from those fish, they will not have any offspring, and we do not need a genetics sample.

Notes on Daily Collection Label (Below)

1. Completed label will be placed in the ziplock bag with all of the samples from that day of sampling
2. Location is the collection location (e.g. Salmon River Hatchery or Black River)
3. Date is the date the samples are taken on (dd/mm/yyyy)
4. Day of sampling: Day 1 would be the first day of sampling, 2 would be the second and so on.
5. Collector: Who collected the genetics samples and filled out this form?
6. First ID #: The ID number on the tube that the first genetic sample for the day was put in.
7. Last ID #: The ID number on the tube that the last genetic sample for the day was put in.
8. # of fish sampled: The total number of genetic samples taken for the day.

Chinook Genetics Daily Collection Label

Location: _____ Date (dd/mm/yyyy): _____

Day of Sampling: _____ Collector: _____

First ID #: _____ Last ID #: _____ # of fish sampled: _____

Notes on Daily Sample Log (Below)

1. This must be filled out daily, but does not need to be filled out for every fish. You only need to record the ID number if the is an anomaly during the sample collection.
2. Date is the date the samples are taken on (dd/mm/2021)
3. Location is the collection location (e.g. Salmon River Hatchery)
4. Collector: Who collected the genetics samples and filled out this form?
5. Day of sampling: Day 1 would be the first day of sampling, 2 would be the second and so on.
6. Data Sheet Number: Only fill out if you need to use multiple daily logs due to a lack of space on the first one.
7. For each subset of fish – fish processed between rounds of sorting – record the first ID number for the subset (Start ID) and the last ID number for the subset (End ID)
 - a. Occasionally sorting may happen concurrently with processing, all of these fish can be considered part of the same subset.
8. For each subset of fish record if any ID numbers are skipped, the ID number of any female fish whose eggs are not combined with another set of eggs prior to fertilization (“singles”), and any other issues.
 - a. For figuring out genetics it is useful to know if the offspring of two female fish are potentially half-siblings and share a father. By tracking the subsets and sequentially labeling all of the mothers, we can get a pretty good idea of which female fish may have half-sibling offspring. That’s why it is important to know which female fish are not paired or if an ID is skipped.
9. Additional notes is for non-sample specific issues, such as accidentally skipping some tubes or if you run out of space on the data subset line.
10. If there are no issues put: No Issues in the Additional Notes section

CHINOOK SALMON GENETIC SAMPLING 2021 DAILY LOG

Date (dd/mm/yyyy): _____ Day of Sampling: _____

Location: _____ Collector: _____

Sex: Females Only Data Sheet Number: ____/____

Subset	Start ID	End ID	Notes (record ID of single fish or if an ID number is skipped)
1			
2			
3			
4			
5			
6			
7			
8			
9			
10			
11			
12			

Additional Notes:

Reference images

Labeled microcentrifuge tubes in a microcentrifuge rack.

Clip a 1cm piece of the adipose fin for genetics.

Notes on Sample Key (below)

1. This must be filled out daily, and it may be best to fill it out for every fish that a genetic sample is taken from
2. Date is the date the samples are taken on (dd/mm/2021)
3. Location is the collection location (e.g. Salmon River Hatchery)
4. Recorder: who is the person filling out this data sheet?
5. Bio Data collector: NYSDEC personnel who is recording the corresponding biologic data
6. Genetic collector: who is collecting the genetic samples?
7. Day of sampling: Day 1 would be the first day of sampling, 2 would be the second, and so on.
8. Data Sheet Number: You will likely use multiple data sheets in a single day as there is only space for 44 fish per data sheet. So if you use 3 data sheets in one day the first data sheet should be labeled "1 / 3".
9. Genetic ID number – this should match the ID number on the vial the genetic sample is put into.
10. Biologic Data ID number – this should match the ID number that Scott Prindle (or whoever is sampling the fish) is using to track the fish they are processing.
11. Biologic data is not taken for every female fish that genetic data is taken from, in these cases put "NA" or "None" down for the Biologic Data ID.
12. Genetic samples are not taken from every fish that biological data is taken from, specifically if a fish is "hard" – eggs are not ready – then that fish is discarded and no genetic sample is taken. In these cases, simply put "NA" or "None" down for the genetic ID number.

APPENDIX 2: TARGETED CONTIGS AND SEQUENCING PRIMERS

The attached excel file (appx2_primers_contigs.xlsx) contains information on the microsatellite marker panel. The 61 loci retained for the final pilot analyses are described including information on the primers, tetrarepeats, and the performance of the markers. Sheets “Primers” and “Performance” are reproduced from the supplemental material included in Fitzpatrick et al. 2023.

APPENDIX 3: SAMPLE ID INFORMATION

Description of the samples used in the pilot analyses and the 2022 analyses including if the sample is a broodmother or offspring, year of collection, and location of collection.

APPENDIX 4: HAPLOTYPE ASSIGNMENT TO SAMPLE FILES

Two .txt files are generated by the Cornell University BioTech custom pipeline per locus. The first file, “Locus[number].haplotypes”, has the sequence each unique haplotype corresponds to and the number of reads across the pool samples. The second file, “Locus[number].haplotype2sample”, shows the number of reads that each sample had per unique haplotype.

APPENDIX 5: CHINOOK SALMON GENOTYPES

These are the generated Chinook Salmon genotype files from the included R script (Appendix 7) formatted to be read into Cervus. The number for the unique haplotypes are specific to each analysis, the “Locus[number].haplotypes” files should be used to get the specific sequence associated with each haplotype number and allow for comparison across analyses. Each row is a sample included in the analyses and each column starting with “LOCUS” is an allele. Missing data is represented by a “?” which, without quotation marks, is a missing data signifier for Cervus.

APPENDIX 6: CERVUS FILES

The .xlsx files are the results of the Cervus analyses, edited to include summary data, remove extraneous columns, and add information on specimen origin and assignment. The remaining files are the input files for Cervus (genotypes, mothers, offspring) and various Cervus outputs: “allele_freq” is the output of the allele frequency analysis, “sim_pa” are the simulated parentage analysis results, and “pa_out” are the parentage analysis results.

APPENDIX 7: R CODE FOR FILTERING AND DATA GENERATION

The R script for filtering the unique haplotypes and preparing the data to be run in Cervus.